

Supplementary material

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Table 1 presents a proposal of structural similarities, to help transfer knowledge from the base domain (food) to the target one (digital).

Table 1

A proposal of structural similarities between the food and digital domains in education.

Food sovereignty principles applied in education	Digital sovereignty principles applied in education
BENEFITS FOR PEOPLE	
<p>Health effects associated with food known and applied to promote certain educational values and habits within and outside school.</p> <p>Examples: positive effects of certain habits (e.g. number of daily vegetables) or negative (e.g. processed food) promoted in school activities</p>	<p>Educational and mental effects of the interaction and use of ICTs known and applied to promote certain education values and habits within and outside school.</p> <p>Examples: positive effects of broadened access to knowledge or negative effects of addictive behaviors due to specific ICT features (e.g. addiction)</p>
<p>Culturally appropriate food, considering both respecting cultural sensitivities in school activities.</p> <p>Examples: diverse options in school menus) and its use as a powerful cultural bridge (e.g. bringing different foods and their meanings to class)</p>	<p>Culturally appropriate technologies, considering both promoting cultural diversity and richness and as a bridge to individual contexts and interests.</p> <p>Examples: digital storytelling activities to share family stories, access to multilingual and diverse educational or cultural resources, virtual learning and exchange programs</p>
<p>Accessibility of food, considering aspects such as costs (e.g. lunch programs for more vulnerable students to guarantee access to adequate food) or personal issues such as health (e.g. different menus according to allergies).</p> <p>Food represented and managed as a right</p>	<p>Accessibility and inclusiveness of ICT tools used considering aspects such as cost (e.g. programs to guarantee access to digital infrastructure, resources, promotion of open educational resources), different needs (e.g. assistive technologies, inclusive content creation and use) and or portability (e.g. use of open standards, guarantee cross-platform compatibility).</p> <p>Access to knowledge and ICT as a right</p>
<p>Relation between food and body representation explicitly considered and addressed along educational activities, with special awareness in their identification and contact with other community services, such as the medical domain (e.g. eating disorders)</p>	<p>Negative effects (e.g. cyberbullying) or problems from effects in technology use considered and addressed, linking with other specialists as needed (bubble, FOMO)</p>
CONTROL	
<p>Food safety, ranging from individual habits covered as part of educational</p>	<p>Technological safety and security, ranging from educational activities</p>

Food sovereignty principles applied in education	Digital sovereignty principles applied in education
activities (e.g. hand washing) to infrastructural aspects (all the domains considered in food practices, including storage, preparation, consumption and disposal)	around safe ICT use, or the multiple ways by which unsafe ICT use can lead to undesired educational, individual or societal issues (e.g. misinformation). Safety and security of the infrastructure, including interaction with technologies adequate to the age of students, compliance with legal and ethical requirements (e.g. personal data handling) and structural (e.g. cyberattacks)
Local producers are situated at the heart of policies	Technologies defined, developed or validated by and for the educational community (i.e. open communities)
Negative industrial practices identified and explained as part of educational activities, and discouraging their consumption as part of habit formation. Examples: The bliss point, the industrial practice of combining an optimal amount of ingredients like sugar, salt, or fat in food that maximizes its palatability, with addictive implications and links with overconsumption, obesity or other health problems and, more generally, affecting consumer's	Negative industrial practices identified and explained as part of educational activities, and discouraging their consumption as part of habit formation. Examples: Deceptive designs, that exploit human psychology and vulnerabilities to manipulate user behavior. This can include dark patterns embedded in user interface (confirmshaming, roach motel by which getting out of a service is more difficult than getting it, trick questions oriented to manipulate user responses, etc), algorithmic deception, data deception (such as hidden data collection, misleading policies or unconsented data brokerage) or social engineering deception (such as baiting)
Transparent processes / results (informed decisions by consumers, from resources needed to produce to consumption)	Transparency of technologies, including aspects such as data extraction and use (i.e. informed parental control)
SUSTAINABILITY	
Environmental impact on the food chain. Examples: avoid food waste, avoid the use of plastics	Environmental impact on the ICT chain. Examples: promote principles of reduction, reuse or recycling (for instance, by the promotion of repairable devices)
CRITICAL SKILLS	
Identified objective is to influence what happens outside schools, including current habits of the families of students, and the future behavior of the students along all activities and mobilizing all possible educational activities (educational content, food products, community interactions, school and community policies, infrastructure, etc)	Identified objective is to influence what happens outside schools, including current habits of the families of students, and the future behavior of the students along all activities and mobilizing all possible educational activities (educational content, food products, community interactions, school and community policies, infrastructure, etc)